

3D NETWORK GRAPHENE INTERLAYER IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES: EXCELLENT INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND STRENGTH

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Keywords: Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), Network graphene interlayer, Fracture toughness, Interfacial strength, Fractography

ABSTRACT

This paper reports our recent work on developing a novel CVD grown 3D network graphene interleaves in glass fiber reinforced composites (GFRPs) with excellent interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength. By incorporating the network graphene in the failure-prone mid-plane, the interleaved multiscale composites present a remarkable increases of 70% and 206% in mode I and II interlaminar fracture toughness, respectively, and 36% enhancement in interlaminar shear strength, when compared to those composites without the interleaves. The pertinent mechanisms responsible for the toughening effects of interleaves include crack deflection and formation of interfacial micro-cracks with significant increase in surface areas owing to the 3D hollow sphere-like graphene wrapping around the epoxy matrix as well as graphene fracture and slippage between adjacent layers. This work opens a new venue towards the development of 3D network graphene interleaved FRPs with excellent toughness and high ILSS for suppression of crack growth under delamination loading compared to its CNT and CNF counterparts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced epoxy composite (FRP) laminates are widely used in aircraft, marine and infrastructure components owing to their high specific strength and stiffness. However, delamination initiation from the edges and junctions, accompanied by subsequent propagation in service may damage the in-plane strength and stiffness, hence potentially jeopardizing the overall structural integrity. Two effective ways to improve delamination resistance include stitching [1,2]/z pinning [3,4] and inserting interleaves at the failure-prone regions of the laminate. Among them, incorporation of nanofiller incorporated polymer thin films or bucky papers, such as graphene oxide and carbon nanofibers, is considered most promising and widely studied recently [5,6], displaying different

properties from typically thermoplastic nanofiber counterparts[7] with simultaneous enhancements in interlaminar fracture toughness and uncompromised in-plane flexural. Key issues involving these carbon nanofillers are the poor dispersability of nanofillers, especially at high loading, weak wetting and affinity with host polymer in the presence of micron-scale fibers due to their inert chemical properties. Lack of dispersion and weak interface bonding strength is always detrimental to achieving the desired effects on mechanical, toughness and other important properties, hindering their applications in polymer composites.

More recently, a three-dimensional (3D) network graphene by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of atomic carbon on a reticulated Ni template, followed by removing the Ni template but preserve the network structure, has gained increasing interest for applications in different areas, especially as promising nanofillers in polymer composites owing to its peculiar 3D integrated structure and excellent electrical conductivity, ultimately overcoming the problems associated with graphene agglomeration while imparting multifunctional properties to the composites [8]. However, the practical application of 3D network graphene/polymer is still at its infant stage and very few studies have appeared in the open literature reporting their properties.

This work is dedicated to developing a novel 3D network graphene interleaved GFRPs with high interlaminar fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength. Three-step process employed here is impregnation of epoxy resin into the 3D network graphene, followed by β -stage curing of the resin and then incorporating the as-prepared interleaf into the mid-plane of GFRP laminates, co-curing to fabricate the 3D network graphene interleaved GFRP. Excellent interlaminar fracture toughness and shear strength of the composites were revealed. Special focus was placed on studying the toughening mechanisms of the composites arising from the interconnected graphene network structure.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Composite processing

The freestanding 3D network graphene was prepared by CVD method [8]. A CH_4 concentration of 1.4 vol% in total gas flow was chosen for growth, giving out approximately four layer number of graphene in average.

The β -stage cured interleaves is processed as follows: Araldite-F (Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol A, Huntsman) and curing hardener piperidine (Sigma-Aldrich) were mixed by moderate stirring at 90 °C in a weight ratio of 100:5 in the fume hood. The mixture was subsequently cast into one layer of 3D network graphene on release paper and β -stage curing in a 120 °C oven for 3.5 h, maintaining the structure integrity for handling and ensuring good bonding between interleaves and newly introduced epoxy/piperidine mixture during the following co-curing process. High strength unidirectional glass fiber fabrics (Nanjing fiberglass R&D Institute, SWU 173-100J, with an area density of 170 g/m²) were utilized as the reinforcement in the GFRP. 3.4 mm thick laminates with 28 plies of fabrics were prepared based on a solvent-less hand lay-up. The whole process was maintained at ~90 °C to ensure low viscosity and good liquidity to fully impregnate the glass fiber fabrics. One layer of β -stage cured 3D network graphene/epoxy interleaf was embedded in the mid-plane of the laminates and a 25 μm thick polyimide film was inserted ahead the interleave serving as an initial crack. The laminates were then wrapped with a breather and release film within a vacuum bag, vacuumed 90 °C for 1 h followed by co-curing in a hot press (0.7 MPa) at 120 °C for 16 h. The resultant composite was slowly cooled to ambient before removal from the hot press. The average thickness of the final interleaf in the fully cured GFRP laminate was $\sim 300 \pm 15 \mu\text{m}$ and the fiber volume fraction was $\sim 60\%$.

Figure 1. Schematic for the fabrication of multiscale 3D network graphene interleaved GFRP.

2.1 Characterization and mechanical testing

The crack growth and fracture morphology of the composites were observed by an optical microscope (Olympus BX51M) and a SEM (JEOL JSM-6700F) with a 5 kV accelerating, respectively. The internal pore structure of 3D network graphene was observed by micro Xradia XCT-400 at 40 kV with 1 mm resolution. 2000 projection images were recorded over 360° with an exposure time of 15 s for each image, providing the inter-connectivity of pores by isolating and extracting the pore skeleton. Images were reconstructed with the software of the micro CT system and a 3D viewer (Xradia) was used to produce the 3D volume rendering (Figure 2c and d). Mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness values were measured using the double-cantilever-beams (DCB) and three-point end notched flexure (ENF) tests at ambient temperature on an Instron 5567 machine, following ASTM D5528-01 for mode I interlaminar fracture toughness tests and the ESIS protocol for mode II interlaminar fracture toughness tests, respectively [9]. Both DCB and ENF samples were 160 mm long × 20 mm wide × 3.4 mm thick containing nominally 50 mm length pre-cracks. Five samples were tested for each GFRP with and without interleaves. For Mode I DCB delamination tests, the crack mouth opening displacement rate was 1 mm/min. The initial interlaminar fracture toughness ($G_{IC,ini}$) was obtained from the crack initiation point of the crack growth resistance ($G_{IC}-\Delta a$) curve and the propagation interlaminar fracture toughness ($G_{IC,pro}$) was averaged when crack growth (Δa) increased from 15 to 50 mm. $G_{IC,pro}$ values were chosen for comparison in Table S1 to avoid any effects of the PI film at crack initiation. The mid-plane deflection of the ENF specimens was controlled by a crosshead rate of 1 mm/min and the initial crack length was 25 mm. The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was measured by short beam shear (SBS) test with rectangular specimens of 25 mm long × 10 mm wide × 3.4 mm thick on a universal testing machine (MTS Sintex 10/D) according to ASTM D 2453.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Porous structure of 3D network graphene

The synthesized 3D network graphene are interconnected in a continuous foam architecture, as shown in Figure 2a. Figure 2b present a broken foam end, indicating the ultrathin graphene struts are hollow with a triangular cross-section, and are made of high quality graphene of approximate four layers with the basal-plane parallel to the strut wall surface [8]. The internal structure was reconstructed by virtual slices of micro-CT scan. And a typical single virtual slice shown in Figure 2c indicates the internal pore structure and distribution. Figure 2d shows a reconstructed 3D micro-CT scan of a broken foam end, which agrees well with SEM image in Figure 2b.

Figure 2. SEM images of surface microstructure of (a) 3D network graphene and (b) broken foam end; (c) single micro-CT scan slice of the porous network graphene; and (d) reconstructed 3D micro-CT scan of broken foam end.

3.2 Interlaminar fracture toughness and ILSS of multiscale composites

Mode I fracture toughness (G_{IC}) versus Δa curves for GFRP with and without 3D network graphene interleaves are shown in Figure 3a. Two distinct differences between them are: (a) There is a continuous increase in the crack growth resistance for control GFRP owing to the progressive accumulation of fiber bridging behind the crack tip [10], whereas a sharp increase in G_{IC} at the initial crack propagation zone is observed, which is followed by moderate reductions with further crack growth for GFRP with interleaves. Similar reductions in G_{IC} are also noted for woven/chopped fiberglass reinforced epoxy composites [11]; (b) The smooth rising R curve seen in control GFRP indicates the crack propagates in a stable manner due to the effect of crack-wake fiber bridging, while the crack in interleaved GFRP advances in an unstable “stick-slip” fashion as it progressively traverses the 3D network graphene [12]. The average initiation and propagation, $G_{IC,ini}$ and $G_{IC,pro}$, toughness values for control GFRP are 340 and 950 J/m², respectively, which correlate well with published values for GFRP [11]. Addition of 3D network graphene interleaves into GFRP increases sharply both $G_{IC,ini}$ and $G_{IC,pro}$ to 1100 and 1620 J/m², corresponding to ~220 and 70% enhancements in mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, respectively (Figure 3b).

The incorporation of 3D network graphene interleaves in GFRP also yields a significant effect on the mode II delamination toughness G_{IIC} , showing a dramatic 206% increase in G_{IIC} compared to control GFRP; also, the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) is increased by ~36% for interleaved GFRP from 46.1 to 62.5 MPa (see Figure 3c). These results signify a higher positive sensitivity of the interleaves on G_{IIC} than on ILSS. Similar observations were reported for CFRP composites interleaved with CNF bucky paper [6]. Further, to identify the benefits of 3D network graphene interleaves, improvements in G_{IIC} and ILSS of interleaved epoxy-based FRPs containing CNTs and

CNFs, stitched and nanofiller-filled FRPs taken from the literature are compared with the present study (Figure 3d). Amongst many different toughening techniques, stitching always show large enhancements in interlaminar fracture toughness but lose 0-17% ILSS [13]. The performance of FRPs containing CB-epoxy thin film [14] or CNF bucky paper interleaves [6] are impressive with synergistic enhancements in both ILSS and toughness. However, improvements are largely impaired at higher nanofiller contents due to the deteriorated dispersion. By contrast, the performance of 3D network graphene interleaved GFRP is best and much better than its CNT and CNF counterparts (see Figure 3d). The above comparisons indicate clearly that more effective interlaminar toughening and strengthening can be achieved with network graphene due to the integrated 3D structure which eliminates the dispersion issue with nanofillers.

Figure 3. (a) Typical crack growth resistance ($G_{IC}-\Delta a$) curves for mode I interlaminar fracture, and (b) G_{IC} for initiation and propagation of GFRP laminates with and without interleaves; (c) Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IIC} and ILSS; and (d) comparison of gains in G_{IIC} and ILSS of interleaved fiber reinforced epoxy-based composites taken from literature [2,6,14–21].

3.3 Toughening mechanisms

Mode I fracture surfaces of GFRP with and without interleaves are shown in Figure 4 to elucidate the ameliorating effect in G_{IC} , which reveal well-defined distinctions between them. The control GFRP fracture surface illustrates characteristic brittle failure in epoxy, and weakly bonded glass fiber/epoxy interface revealing quite clean fiber surfaces (see red and blue arrows, respectively, in Figure 4a) confirming low resistance to crack propagation. By contrast, the interleaved GFRP presents rugged, multiphase fractures with numerous areas equivalent in sizes to the circular cells between the 3D graphene network (red and yellow arrows indicate epoxy and the surrounding graphene, respectively, in Figure 4b-d). Closer examination shows sites of river marks owing to fracture initiation, followed by smooth surfaces due to crack growth on epoxy along the walls of graphene (Figure 4d) when the crack breaks the graphene network. Three major roles of 3D network graphene interleaves on improving G_{IC} of GFRP can be identified below. (a) When the crack advances within the interleaf, its crack front will deflect and/or twist upon meeting and breaking the interconnected walls of the

Figure 4. Typical scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of mode I fracture surface in the crack propagation region of (a) control GFRP and (b-d) interleaved GFRP. Crack propagation direction is indicated by white arrows.

graphene network followed by collapse of graphene (see yellow arrows in Figure 4c). This yields a tortuous crack path with enhanced fracture surface area, thus increasing the fracture energy absorption [8]. (b) Micro-cracks occur along the interfaces of network graphene/epoxy owing to the moderate interfacial bonding without any functionalization of graphene (see red dotted ovals in Figure 4c) contribute to the total fracture energy [22,23]. (c) When the crack tip encounters the edges of graphene, the occurrence of slippage and separation in adjacent layers caused by the disturbance of the weak van der Waals forces between them also contributes to further energy absorption (see orange circle in Figure 4c) [24]. Among them, crack deflection and twisting is identified as the primary toughening mechanism owing to the high aspect ratio of 3D graphene network. Similar effect have also been suggested by previous studies, showing enhanced toughness of graphene/epoxy nanocomposites compared to other conventional filler counterparts [25].

Typical mode II interlaminar shear fracture surface of interleaved GFRP also presents different morphologies when compared to control GFRP, featuring corrugated, multi-planar fractures with characteristic multi-directional shear hackles with higher intensity in the epoxy inside each pore of network graphene, propagating along the boundaries of graphene struts (Figure 5a and b; see yellow arrows for graphene struts and red arrows for hackles). Higher intensity of hackles means larger fracture surface areas, thus more energy absorption during fracture [9]. As the crack tip advances, due to its interactions with interconnected graphene, interfacial failure and broken graphene (see red oval and dotted yellow arrows in Figure 5c) are observed. All these failure mechanisms will contribute to higher G_{IIC} obtained for interleaved GFRP. By contrast, the fracture surface for control GFRP only shows shear hackles between neighboring glass fibers (see red arrows in Figure 5d).

Figure 5. SEM images of mode II fracture surface of (a-c) interleaved GFRP and (d) control GFRP. Crack growth direction is indicated by white arrow.

Figure 6. (a, b) Typical side-view micrographs of crack growth and (c) SEM image of the upper edge of interleaved GFRP ENF test sample.

Further work was done on the crack growth behavior in the interleaved GFRP as observed from the side towards the thickness direction of the ENF specimens (see Figures 6). The crack displays a meandering path with significant and frequent deflections, confirming a considerable amount of fracture energy is absorbed during crack growth, compared to a typical straight crack path of the

control FRPs [6]. A magnified image in Figure 6b reveals a distinct zig-zag crack path entirely within the 3D network graphene interleaf; crack growth along the interface between the interleaf and adjacent fiber rich laminates is discouraged due to the strong adhesion between them. Note that the characteristic curved triangular and dog-bone graphene appear in the interleaf (red arrows in Figures 6b), evidence of 3D network graphene resembling the profile of the reticulated Ni template. Crack deflection occurs when the advancing crack tip meets the walls of network graphene: it either follows the contour of the triangular or dog-bone shaped graphene with continuously varied directions (Figure 6b); or it is impinged by the wall of graphene and grows along the graphene/epoxy interface with subsequent failure of the graphene struts revealing quite clean graphene/epoxy interface in Figure 6c. The image of the upper crack surface depicts clear graphene strut failure and graphene/epoxy interface debonding (see yellow dotted arrow and red oval, respectively, in Figure 6c), in addition to crack deflection, as the operative toughening mechanisms.

4. CONCLUSION

We report an effective interlaminar toughening and strengthening of GFRP by incorporation of 3D network graphene for suppression of crack growth under delamination loading. The fracture surface and side-view morphology were evaluated to account for the enhanced toughness. A summary of made in the following.

- (i) Mode I and II interlaminar fracture toughness can reach 1620 and 2540 J/m², respectively, which correspond to impressive 70% and 206% improvements over those of control GFRP, and 36% increase in ILSS.
- (ii) For mode I loading, crack tip deflection due to the network graphene functioning as crack arresters and crack propagation controlled by the network graphene microstructure, resulting in multi-plane fracture surface with an effectively larger surface area leading to higher G_{IC} .
- (iii) For mode II loading, matrix shear hackles are the major toughening mechanism for both control and interleaved GFRPs, but the latter laminates have a higher intensity of multi-directional shear hackles, thereby contributing to the enhanced fracture toughness G_{IIC} .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was conducted when JJ was a Visiting Scholar at the University of Sydney from Hong Kong University of Science & Technology (HKUST) and partially supported by the Australian Research Council (Discovery Project DP130104648). Technical assistance and access to facilities at the Australian Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis in Sydney and the Materials Characterization and Preparation Facilities in HKUST are much appreciated.

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